

PRESENT PRACTICE OF SHEABUTTER PROCESSING IN NORTH- EASTERN NIGERIA: (A CASE STUDY OF GATAMWARWA VILLAGE[†])

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ABSTRACT

Gatamwarwa is a village under Chibok Local Government Area of Borno State in North eastern Nigeria. Sheabutter production is one of the occupations of women in this village. A study was carried out on the traditional method of processing sheabutter in this village. Seven major operations are involved in the production process- collection of nuts, sorting/burning of nuts, cracking of nuts, winnowing to separate the kernel from the shell, cleaning of kernel using rag, crushing of kernel to form paste using mortar and pestle and extraction of fat. All the operations are currently carried out manually and are inefficient (as it only extracts about 20 % fat), tedious and time consuming. The problems associated with this processing method were identified and solutions that will improve the quality and quantity of the product were proposed.

KEY WORDS: Gatamwarwa, sheabutter, cracking, kernel, kneading, extraction.

INTRODUCTION

Sheanut tree (*Butyrospermum paradoxum*) is a small deciduous tree, which grows naturally in wooden Savannah region through out West Africa (FAO, 2003). The tree begins to bear fruits at 12-15 years. It grows to a height of 7-13 m and has a thick trunk with a number of spreading branches, which form a dense crown. The fruits produced are ellipsoidal, 4-6 cm long with fleshy pulp, which taste like pear and usually one-seeded. The fruits are ready for harvesting from August-September (FAO, 2003). The seed is about 2.5-5 cm long, shining, dark-brown with a white scar on one side. It is removed after decomposition of the pulp or after drying. The seed contains about 45-60% fat and 9% protein (Purseglove, 1979). In Nigeria, sheanut is obtained abundantly in Oyo, Osun, Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe states (Oluwole, 2004). The locally extracted fat from sheanut kernel is known as sheabutter and it is referred to differently depending on the locality where it is produced. The Yorubas refer to it as 'Oori', the Hausas call it 'Manka-danya', and Fulanis and Arabs call it 'Karehi' and 'Quariti' respectively (Lewicki, 1974). Peter and Ann (1992) reported that sheabutter is used as a cooking fat, illuminant, medical ointment, hairdressing cream, body cream and a raw material for the manufacture of soap, candle and cosmetic products. It also serves a constituent of filling for chocolate creams. At present, there is no plantation of sheanut and little information is available on the existence of commercial plants for the purpose of processing the oil (Koku, 1989). Sheanut is the third most produced oil seed after groundnut and palm kernel (CBN, 2001). Table 1 shows the estimated output of major oil seed/nut in Nigeria.

Sheanut is an important oil crop. Marchand (1988) reported that, in Europe, sheanut is used for the production of butter. The cake can be used as a base for dyes or as a water proof when applied to a clay house. It can also be applied as fertilizer, or burned as fuel. Even the resulting ashes can be used to make potash. However, the present status of sheanut processing remains the extraction of sheabutter, which is performed by women and children, using traditional methods of extraction (Adgidzi *et al*, 2003). A photograph of sheanuts and kernels is shown in Figure1.

There is however a need to develop the sheanut processing industry in the North-Eastern Nigeria and sensitize the local processors. This paper reports the present practice of sheabutter processing in the North-eastern Nigeria and highlights the possible ways to improve the processing method.

METHOD OF SHEABUTTER PROCESSING IN NORTH-EASTERN NIGERIA

Purseglove (1979) reported that the production of sheabutter in West Africa has been estimated at 0.5 million tons per year. Anon (1985) reported that Mali, one of the leading producers of sheanut produces 150- 200 metric tons of nuts per annum.

Table 1: Estimated output of major oilseed/nut in Nigeria (1000 tonnon)

Oilseed/nut	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001
Groundnut	2101	2222	2309	2390	2401
Palm kernel	550	572	600	629	620
Sheanut	373	369	421	448	457
Melon	320	328	340	352	354
Cotton seed	309	329	351	353	358
Coconuts	154	167	175	181	183
Benniseed	69	78	30	82	83

Source: CBN (2001)

The current production may be around 250 metric tons annually (FAO, 2003). The principal exporters of the nuts are Mali, Burkina Faso, Benin Republic, Senegal, Cote D ' Ivoire, Ghana, Gambia and Nigeria. Holland and Belgium used to be the main importers, but currently, most of the produce goes to the United Kingdom, Japan and Denmark. Despite the economic importance of sheabutter, it is not produce commercially in the North-Eastern Nigeria (Oluwole *et al*, 2007). According to Lewicki (1974) the traditional procedures are inefficient, as they only permit the extraction of 25- 27% fat from the kernel. The traditional procedures presently practice in this region permit the extraction of about 20%fat from the kernel which is very inefficient and time consuming. These procedures involve the following steps:

i. Collection and drying of nuts-

Fruits and nuts whose fruits are eaten by animals are normally collected together from wild (Figure 2) the nuts are later sorted out for processing while those with fruits are left to decompose leaving only the nuts. The nuts are dried by exposing them to sun and wind in shallow layer on the ground. After drying, the nuts are packed in a container for further process.

Figure 1: Sheanut and Kernel (A, Nut and B, kernel). (source Aviara *et al*, 2005)

Figure 2: Dried sheanut in a container

ii. Sorting and burning of nuts-

The remains of dried fruits and unwanted materials such as stones and dirt are removed from the nuts by hand. The cleaned nuts are then spread on the ground and covered with combustible agricultural waste materials for burning. The burning is done in order to reduce the moisture content of the nut/kernel to ease the cracking as reported by Oluwole *et al* (2007). Figure 3 shows the method used in the study area.

Figure 3: burning of nuts

Figure 4: Shelling of nut

iii. Cracking of nut/winning-

Cracking of nuts to obtain clean kernel is carried out by the use of stones and woods (Lucas, 1991). Philips (1977) reported that this method could handle sheanut at the rate of about 14 kg/h including the separation of

shells. The use of pestle and mortar to crack the nut was reported by Oluwole (2004) of callable to handling 110 kg of nuts per day including winnowing. Winnowing is achieved by holding baskets filled with mixture of seeds and shells at arm length and gradually emptying them. If there is strong wind, the pieces of shell will be blown away, if not, the operation is repeated many times (Fleury, 1985). Figure 4 shows the cracking method used in the study area.

iv. Cleaning of kernel-

Cleaning of kernel is done with the aid of clothing material, this is the method wildly used in the study area (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Cleaning of kernels

v. Crushing of kernel-

Crushing of kernel to form paste is normally done by women using pounding mortar and pestle (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Crushing of kernel

Figure 7: kneading to form dough

vi. Extraction of fat from the kernel paste involves:

a. kneading, this is done by pressing and squeezing the paste with hand to form dough (Figure 7).

b. boiling in water mixed with potash-

The dough is introduced into the boiling water as soon as the water starts boiling (Figure 8).

Figure 8: a- introducing diluted potash b- introducing the dough into boiling water

c. Scooping off the fat-

After boiling for about 20 minutes oil starts floating on the boiling water. The floating oil is then scooped off into an empty dried container (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Scooping off the fat

Figure 10: Drying of oil

d. drying of fat by heating-

Wiemer and Korthals (1989) and Oluwole (2004) reported that drying is done by heating to 130 °C to remove all traces of moisture. The adopted method in the study area is by heating until there is no more cracking sound of water molecules this is done by experience. Figure 10 shows the collected dried oil.

As could be observed, all the operations mentioned above are currently carried out manually. Table 2 shows the results obtained from five different local sheabutter processors in Gatamwarwa village. From Table 2 it is observed that about 18.54% fat was obtained, which is about 30.9% of the fat present in the kernel (Oluwole, *et al* 2007). This shows that the traditional method of sheabutter extraction is inefficient, tedious and time-consuming. It is therefore necessary to develop an appropriate technology for the processing of sheabutter to provide the needed solutions to problems facing the local processors of sheabutter in this part of Nigeria.

Table 2: Results of sheabutter obtained from five processors

S/N	Mass of sheanut (kg)	Mass of kernel (kg)	Mass of sheabutter (kg)
1.	9.10	7.55	1.41
2.	12.10	10.00	1.91
3.	11.63	9.85	1.68
4.	18.51	15.35	2.94
5.	10.32	8.55	1.57
Sum	61.66	51.13	10.87
Av.	12.33	10.26	1.902 ± 0.608

PROBLEMS AND CONSTRAINTS OF SHEABUTTER PROCESSING IN NORTH-EASTERN NIGERIA

There are several problems and constraints confronting or limiting the processing of sheabutter in terms of quantity, quality and profitability in this region. Some of these problems are as follows:

a. problems associated with the unit operations involved in the processing procedures.

i. lack of plantation of sheanut.

Sheanuts are collected by searching under the scattered trees in the wild. Individual control over scattered trees are not possible, this invariably affects the quantity of sheanuts obtain per individual processor.

ii. lack of processing equipment.

As could be observed, all the unit operations involved in the processing of sheanut are currently carried out manually in the North- eastern Nigeria. These unit operations are laborious and time consuming, most especially crushing of the kernel with mortar and pestle which could not give fine particles for efficient fat extraction (Oluwole, 2004). As a result, the present status of sheanut processing remains the extraction of sheabutter, which is performed by women and children, using traditional methods of extraction.

iii. lack of commercial processing plants

Lack of commercial processing plants is not encouraging people to go into sheabutter business.

b. problems associated with government policies

i. lack of government promotional programmes

There is no promotional program for sheanut production like other crops such as cassava, rice, etc.

ii. Lack of control body for sheanut products

There is no regulatory body to oversee the activities of the sheanut processors for example sheanut farmers association and sheanut market board.

iii. Unavailability of standard or organized market for sheanut products

THE WAY FORWARD

For these problems to be solved, the three tiers of government have a lot to do.

i Government should encourage the plantation of sheanut

ii Government and private sectors should invest on and encourage the fabrication of processing equipment through appropriate technology initiatives

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